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WEB USAGE MINING FOR IMPROVE WEB BASED LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The Web offers several opportunities in the field of education. With the immense expansion of information available on the web, web mining has become appropriate for the web based learning systems. Learning through Online is one of the practical modes of education. Learning Websites, essential courses, Web supported instructional shells, and E-books are some of the modes of delivering the Online Learning. Web mining is the series of task used for mining or extracting useful information from the web pages or web sites. It provides intrinsic knowledge of teaching and learning process for effective education planning by applying various techniques/tools. This paper discusses the benefits and usefulness of web usage mining methods in online learning environment.

Keywords: Web usage mining, E-Learning, Web Based Environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Early stages of Learning takes place the class room learning, Other than class room those who are interested using the Library to gather more knowledge after that the usage of ICT are take place , for the improvement of web applications Learning process also enhanced and use the web technology for Learning process. From the Web based Learner to Web Based Learning content provider have the different components and use the different techniques to fulfill their needs as well for the success of technology and skill implementation.

The information provider or those who are willing to deliver the message to others either the organized sectors or individuals use the web technology to upload their content. After the uploaded process organization/individuals are awaiting the how the content should reach to the society/learner. It should be analyzed, for that process the most powerful technology data mining in specific Web Mining WM are used that purpose. The Web mining are divided into further they are listed below,

1. Web Content Mining
2. Web Structure Mining
3. Web Usage Mining

Web Usage Mining uses many tools for analyze the web logs, the web logs are available in different stages client-level logs, proxy-level logs, server-level logs and content-level logs the flow of logs are depicted as the following diagram.

Figure. 1. Architecture of log flows in Web Environment

II. METHODOLOGY

The Proposed methodology of the Role of Web Usage Mining in Web Based Learning Environments is depicted in the following figure. Roles are categorized in different levels here five levels are used in the entire process.

Figure. 3. over all architecture for the Role of WUM in WBLE

A. Web based learners

Web Based Learners are a individual/groups of people/a unit of organizations/ a classroom student strength/smart phone user/anybody who access the web based learning content. It is denoted as *Lns*.

B. Web usage mining

WUM consist of the three major steps for mining the webpage or web content access they are;

1. Data Pre-processing
2. Discovery of Web Usage Pattern
3. Pattern Analysis.

1. Data pre-processing

This process takes the inputs from the log files kept in their system in all level of application the data should be stored in any one the location. The stored data can be retrieved and it is used for the next level operations. The data's categorized as Usage Data, Content Data, Structure Data, and User Data. In this stage the following process are used. ie, Data Cleaning, Learner and Session Identification, Path Completion. The following Table 1. Represents the user details which include Browser type, URL, References, Agent, IP and Time. The table 2.Represents the Session details which include the session Id, time, IP, URL, Reference and agent. The table 3 represents the Attribute Definitions for Each Learner.

2. Discovery of web usage pattern

In this stage the accessed web content based on the type either in videos/text/audio which user can access the data, which type of data can be used. Numerical technique is used to abstract information about the website visitors. Then from this abstracted knowledge *Association rule* generates the association between frequently referenced pages and *Sequential pattern* tools helps in predicting future visit patterns. Data *Clustering tools* group's comparable characteristics items together, most concerned groups in web usage mining tasks are image group, cluster, and page group, cluster, and *Classification* tool do the generalization process and combine together into one predefined class.

Table. I. User identification using browser type and IP address

Time	IP	URL	Ref	Agent
0.05	2.3.4.5	A	B	IE8;Win2k
0.08	1.2.3.4	B	--	IE8;WinXP;SP1
0.13	1.2.3.4	C	A	IE8;Win2k
0.14	1.2.3.4	B	C	IE8;Win2k
0.17	1.2.3.4	E	--	IE7;Win2k
0.16	2.3.4.5	C	B	IE8;Win2k
0.21	2.3.4.5	D	A	IE7;WinXP;SP1
0.21	2.3.4.5	A	--	IE8;WinXP;SP1
0.24	1.2.3.4	E	C	IE8;WinXP;SP1
0.24	1.2.3.4	C	A	IE8;Win2k
0.35	2.3.4.5	B	B	IE8;Win2k
0.59	1.2.3.4	D	C	IE7;WinXP;SP1
1.21	1.2.3.4	E	B	IE8;Win2k
1.25	1.2.3.4	A	D	IE7;WinXP;SP1
1.26	2.3.4.5	C	--	IE8;WinXP;SP1
1.27	2.3.4.5	F	C	IE7;WinXP;SP1
1.26	1.2.3.4	F	C	IE8;Win2k
1.31	1.2.3.4	B	A	IE8;Win2k
1.37	1.2.3.4	D	B	IE7;WinXP;SP1

	Time	IP	URL	Ref
	0.05	2.3.4.5	A	B
	0.08	1.2.3.4	B	--
	0.13	1.2.3.4	C	A
User 1	0.14	1.2.3.4	B	C
	0.17	1.2.3.4	E	--
	0.16	2.3.4.5	C	B
	0.21	2.3.4.5	D	A
	0.21	2.3.4.5	A	--

Table.2. Example of identification of sessions

Session 1	0.24	1.2.3.4	E	C	IE8;WinXP;SP1
	0.24	1.2.3.4	C	A	IE8;Win2k
	0.35	2.3.4.5	B	B	IE8;Win2k
	0.59	1.2.3.4	D	C	IE7;WinXP;SP1
Session 2	1.21	1.2.3.4	E	B	IE8;Win2k
	1.25	1.2.3.4	A	D	IE7;WinXP;SP1
	1.26	2.3.4.5	C	--	IE8;WinXP;SP1
	1.27	2.3.4.5	F	C	IE7;WinXP;SP1

Table.3. Attribute Definitions for Each Learner

Name	Description
Average time	It is the average of the time spent by students on the specific topic, within a subject, in the selected data sample registered for the course.
Average Score	It is the average of the marks scored in assessment of each topic, within a subject, by the students in the selected data sample registered for the course
Total Attempts	These are the numbers of times a specific topic within a subject is referred by students in the selected data sample registered for the course
Marks Scored	These are the marks the student obtained in the assessment of a specific topic within a subject
n_assessment	Number of assessments done
n_assess_p	Number of assessments passed
n_assess_f	Number of assessments failed

3. Pattern Analysis

Pattern analysis is the last part of Web Usage Mining. This phase will filter out all unimportant patterns from the set found in the pattern discovery. Information query mechanism, such as Structured Query Language, is the most common form of pattern investigation method. Content and pattern information are also for filtering out patterns containing pages of usage types, content types or pages that match a certain hyperlink structure.

C. Web enabled learning technology

The learning source content are videos and audio/power point presentation are stored in web server which permits to access the user or clients in 24x7 basis, the sources are ready to available to play in multimedia software or power point. Some source provider can give their content or information in free some of them collect some amount. The information accesses are maintained in log file here we follow the operations of log file.

1. Log files

- ✓ **Web Server Log Files:** These log files resides in web server and notes activity of the user browsing website. There are four types of web server logs i.e., transfer logs, agent logs, error logs and referrer logs.
- ✓ **Web Proxy Server Log Files:** These log files contains information about the proxy server from which user request came to the web server.
- ✓ **Client browser Log Files:** These log files resides in client's browser and to store them special software are used

2. Log files parameters

- ✓ Log files contain various parameters which are very useful in recognizing user browsing patterns .Below is the list of some of the parameters.
- ✓ **User Name:** Identifies the user who has visited the website and this identification normally is IP address.
- ✓ **Visiting Path:** It is the path taken by the user while visiting the website.
- ✓ **Path Traversed:** It is the path taken by the user within the website.
- ✓ **Time Stamp:** It is the time spent by user on each page and is normally known as session.
- ✓ **Page Last Visited:** It is the page last visited by the user while leaving the website.
- ✓ **Success Rate:** It is measured by downloads and copying activity carried out on the website.
- ✓ **User Agent:** It is the browser that user uses to send the request to the server.
- ✓ **URL:** It is the resource that is accessed by the user and it may be of any format like HTML, CGI etc.
- ✓ **Request Type:** It is the method that is used by the user to send the request to the server and it can be either GET or POST method.

III. REVIEW OF LITEARTURE

In current Scenario, all communications are made via online; here consider some of the applications done on online process E-commerce, E-Banking, E-Transport Booking and also E-Learning. The mentioned above applications are processed in different levels of operations, such as the sources of applications are have content or information's that is stored in any one of the DBMS, the data's are update after the transactions of each applications.

In [1]. The role of web usage mining in web applications evaluation are analyzed with the some steps of operations, they are data preprocessing, pattern discovery and pattern analysis. For the process of Web usage mining the Hybrid approaches is used in this article which combines the two methods they are the compact HPG (Hyper Probability Grammar) approach with the precise Online Analytical Process [OLAP] approach. In this representation data is stored into a database throughout the XML and Quilt Query. The conational constraints for the examination are built on the top of this database and data together with the constraint are used for modelling HPG, which are then mined using BFS based algorithm for mining the association rules.

In [2], this article represents the four types of problems they are 1.Incomplete or Limited Information Problem, 2. Incorrect Information problem 3.Persistence Problem 4.Incorrect recommendation. To solve the mentioned above issues the implements the following strategy, User Request- User request is processed for search engine to obtain the results. (2) top n Results Extraction – Top n results are extracted from search engine based on the user query. (3) Content mining - Statistical parameters such as a term frequency (TF) are calculated. For this every result is individually analyzed based on keywords and content. The calculations depend on the user query. Every result of the keywords and content words are compared by full word matching. If a match is found then particular weight is awarded to each word. Likewise each link is given the final matching score. (4) Page Reranking- At last, the normalized value of each result is sorted in descending order to get the most relevant content for the user query. Re-ordered results are sent back to the user so that the top most pages are more relevant for the user query.

In [3], this article represents the overall concepts of web mining and in particular describes about the functions of web usage mining preprocessing, pattern analysis and pattern discovery. And describes the applications that depends on the web usage mining are E-Commerce, E-governance and E-Learning Web usage mining is becoming an active interesting field of research because of its prospective commercial benefits. Finally the author analyzed the following factors visitor’s behaviour, web logs, web services and e-services providers tool that satisfy the customer needs.

In [4], this article represents the web usage mining basic operations and also represents source of data for web usage mining, it includes the Server Level Collection, Client Level Collection, and Proxy Level Collection. Finally it was described the operations of web usage mining.

In [5], the chapter 12 of the book Data mining and Its Application represents the following essential concepts basics of web usage mining, process of web usage mining, Key Elements of Web Usage Data Pre-Processing and its sub contents Data Fusion and Cleaning, Page view Identification, User Identification, Sessionization, Path Completion, Data Integration. The further concepts of web usage mining is Data Modeling for Web Usage Mining and Discovery and Analysis of Web Usage Patterns and its sub content is Session and Visitor Analysis, Cluster Analysis and Visitor Segmentation, Association and Correlation Analysis, Analysis of Sequential and Navigational Patterns, Classification and Prediction based on Web User Transactions.

IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Analysis of web server log file from NEFT server resulted in recognition of various patterns. Technique “Converting IP address to domain name” helps in identification of visitor from the country they are sending request to the web server. Pattern recognized from grouping of visitors based on response code is helpful in identifying the visitors causing unnecessary traffic by requesting the web pages that are not available

V. CONCLUSION

Web usage mining is a non-trivial process of extracting useful implicit and previously unknown patterns from the usage of the web. The Significant research is invested to discover these useful patterns to increase effectiveness of e-learning sites. However, the goals of these applications and methods, turning visitors into purchasers, are different from the goals in E-learning; turning learners into efficient better learners.” We have seen some examples where data mining techniques can enhance on-line education for the educators as well as the learners. While some tools using data mining techniques to help educators and learners are being developed, the research is still in its infancy. In addition, with the consciousness of the potential advantages of incorporated web usage mining and the inadequate data recorded by web servers, there is a need for more concentrate logs from the relevance side to enrich the information already logged by the web server.

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